

Cloud-Native Data Formats and Standards

Breakout session board on gaps, needs, and solutions for improving the use of cloud-native data formats and standards.

GAPS

Tools are not ready +4	Proliferation of different data formats can be confusing to data users +4	Unawareness of research communities that could benefit from cloud-native data +1	Is there a standard that facilitates faceted search? +1
Clear guidelines of how prepare and use cloud-native data	Data version control guidance for cloud-native data +9	Mixed or unclear data licenses	Lack of initiative from some research communities may limit general adoption of standards across fields

NEEDS

Better funding for open-source software, especially maintenance +8	Guidance for users +5	Best practices +3	Users need to adopt +1
Adoption at governmental level for cloud-native tech +1	What is in it for me? Economic and societal benefits? +3	Users wanting to switch formats	

SOLUTIONS

Create practical examples that show why the new format is better +12	Data at different levels of abstraction and aggregation	Stop creating even more new standards	EO embeddings (community based)
Data processing in overviews for fast prototyping +2	Connect (via an event) different disciplines to see what already exists and what can be learned, e.g. particle physics, health, astronomy	TDCC-NES ontology engineers?	

Cloud-Native Data Infrastructure

Breakout session board on gaps, needs, and solutions for improving the use of cloud-native data infrastructure.

GAPS

Vendor lock-in +4	Gap between how good US tech is vs EU tech +4	Reliable pricing for cloud processing costs +5	Price increase for memory / GPU +4
Organisations who want to move to the cloud are worried about forecasting / estimating costs +1	Unified solution - now we have lots of separate working parts +1	Version control integration +1	Infrastructure for sensitive / private data, allowing processing in the cloud +1
Traditional US hyperscalers offer sometimes too much and unnecessary +1			

NEEDS

Less reliance on US tech +7	Cost monitoring +1	Money / financing +4	Accessible European infrastructure +4
Energy-aware orchestration +1	Unified jargon (rather than different per vendor) +1	Maintained / curated datasets +2	Maintained / curated datasets +2
European providers developments in service +1	Cloud-native PDOK? +1	Energy monitoring +1	Communicating the message "why cloud-native data solutions" to those with money +1
Service for caching chunks when data is not available at compute provider +1			

SOLUTIONS

Crisis stimulation to change +1	EU cloud provider +1	Bring use to the data +1	Make researchers aware of non-bigtech options +5
Make researchers aware that on-premises is not for free +1	Bigger EU funds +7	One-pager to explain to NWO & government why an investment in cloud-native data solutions is worthwhile (e.g. energy, cost, efficiency) +5	Stop hiring McKinsey and other consultants that just make buzzword PowerPoints +1

Training and Capacity Development for Cloud-Native Data

Breakout session board on gaps, needs, and solutions for improving training and capacity development for cloud-native data.

GAPS

More people / personnel with experience +1	Fragmented learning / course materials +5	Use-case specific advice (e.g. for transition) +3	Maintenance of materials (landscape moves quickly) +5
Rapid changes in technology / standards leads to learning materials becoming outdated quickly	Data version control guidance for cloud-native data +9	Limited public sector adoption +2	Self-directed learning (e.g. video) is not for everyone. Not all data users know where to start or what it relevant to learn +3

NEEDS

Time for professional development	TDOC-NES data carpentry training (there is a project for 50 new instructors. Maybe a lesson on cloud-native data by RSEs & data stewards) +4	Incentives for non-tech researchers to adopt / change +6	Identify who needs training? (researchers/PIs, infrastructure providers, RSEs, data stewards)
Focus in real use cases and applications +5			

SOLUTIONS

More integration among tech people from different organizations to set up training and informative events +5	Budget allocation +5	Collect user feedback, co-design training & implement in future iterations +5	Bring pedagogical & instructional design expertise into training development +1
Continuous training on the adoption of cloud-native solutions	Psychology of change +2	Measure the impact of training at individual & organizational levels	Realise benefits quickly +1
Test projects to try	Produce a roles map to identify responsibilities (this would also make institutions to understand what positions / people / skills are needed)		

